

Exploring the role of predators of mosquitoes and their larvae in the control of mosquito-borne diseases: a scoping review

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Abbreviation List

AMR - Anti-Microbial Resistance

CDC - Centers for Disease Control and Prevention

CDSR - Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews

DDT - Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane

GVCR - Global Vector Control Response

IRMs - Insecticide Resistant Mosquitoes

IVM – Integrated Vector Management

IUCN - International Union for Conservation of Nature

ITNs - Insecticide-treated Nets

MSF - Médecins sans Frontières

MBD - Mosquito-borne diseases

NBS – Nature-based solutions

PRISMA - Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses

PRISMA-ScR - Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses Extension for Scoping Reviews

VBD - Vector-borne diseases

WHO - World Health Organization

Abstract

According to the WHO, vector-borne diseases account for 17% of all infectious diseases resulting in 700,000 deaths each year. The global burden of mosquito-borne diseases (MBDs) is expected to increase dramatically in the near future. Insecticides are the most relied-upon methods to fight MBDs. Newly developed vaccines are a great tool in the arsenal against MBDs, however, vaccines address the consequences of the spread of MBDs, not its causes. The use of *Wolbachia* bacteria while promising is still in the research stages and environmental concerns need to be addressed. Current insecticide-centred practices result in collateral damage to the environment, predators of mosquitoes, and human health, as well as increasing insecticide resistance in mosquitos. Due to climate change, an increasing number of regions around the globe are anticipated to become conducive to mosquitoes and the illnesses they transmit. Consequently, there has been a growing interest in recent years in exploring the potential of nature-based solutions to address MBDs. This paper investigates the effectiveness of mosquito control through the introduction of predators of mosquitoes and their larvae through a scoping review of existing. 92 sources were examined for this review. The findings of the literature search indicate that the most researched predators for biological control roles are fish and copepods, followed by mosquitoes (*Toxorhynchites*) and dragonflies. Other organisms mentioned in the literature include flatworms, salamanders, geckoes, turtles, spiders, backswimmers, heteropteran insects, beetles, tadpoles, shrimps and the Bladderwort plant. Practical challenges to the introduction of predatory species include a lack of knowledge of complicated ecosystem dynamics, including climate, competing predators, and alternative prey. Poorly planned predator intruductions can disrupt the existing balance in ecosystems affecting non-target species and altering the makeup of the ecosystem itself. Lastly, biological control can pose a risk to human health, either through increased contact with wildlife, increasing the risk of transmitting disease, introducing insecticides into the food chain in IVM, or through threats to food security if agricultural practices are affected.

Introduction

Vectors are living organisms that transmit diseases from animals to humans or between humans (WHO, 2019). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), vector-borne diseases (VBDs) result in more than 700,000 deaths globally every year. Moreover, it is estimated that VBDs are responsible for 17% of all infectious diseases (WHO, 2019). VBDs are caused by viruses, parasites and bacteria that are transmitted to humans by living organisms. Common vectors include lice, fleas, sand flies, and ticks, however, mosquitoes are responsible for the biggest share of the global burden of vector diseases. Due to the overuse and misuse of anti-microbial drugs and pesticides, pathogen and vector resistance to these has hampered efforts to eradicate some zoonotic diseases such as malaria (Hemingway, et al., 2004).

Mosquitoes are the animals responsible for the most human deaths, carrying diseases such as Malaria, Dengue fever, Chagas, Zika, Yellow fever, West Nile fever, and Chikungunya among others (WHO, 2019). Particularly, the most concerning vector mosquito species are *Aedes*, *Culex*, and *Anopheles*, responsible for carrying a wide range of MBDs as seen in *Table 1*. Globally over 2.5 billion individuals live in dengue-endemic areas while malaria, the most prevalent mosquito-borne illness, is responsible for over 600,000 deaths worldwide each year. Other diseases such as the ones caused by the Zika virus have seen major outbreaks associated with congenital abnormalities in newborns and posing serious risks to pregnant women (CDC, 2020; CDC, 2021a). Mosquito-borne diseases or MBDs thus have significant mortality, morbidity, and economic cost to societies affected by them as a whole. Moreover, due to a range of different factors, the burden that MBDs place on society is expected to rise.

Table 1:

List of Mosquito species, along with associated diseases and the pathogen that causes the disease in humans

Mosquito Species	Associated Disease	Type of pathogen
<i>Aedes</i>	Chikungunya	Virus
	Dengue	Virus
	Lymphatic filariasis	Parasite
	Rift Valley fever	Virus
	Yellow Fever	Virus
	Zika	Virus
<i>Anopheles</i>	Lymphatic filariasis	Parasite
	Malaria	Parasite
<i>Culex</i>	Japanese encephalitis	Virus
	Lymphatic filariasis	Parasite
	West Nile fever	Virus

Factors contributing to MBDs

Figure 1:

Interaction of meteorological and other determinants of dengue transmission cycles and clinical disease (Cambell-Lendrum, et al., 2015).

Given that the climate is a determinant of MBDs, MBDs disproportionately affect tropical world regions such as South and Southeast Asia, Africa, and South America. The risk of the spread and transmission of MBDs depends on a range of environmental factors such as temperature, humidity, and precipitation, but while these are generally more characteristic of tropical regions, climate change is improving the environmental suitability for mosquitoes and mosquito-borne diseases in regions that were not traditionally at risk. (Colón-Gonzalez et al., 2021).

For example, malaria, the most burdensome of MBD, has become endemic in areas in which it was not endemic previously (Watts et al., 2019). Likewise, as the environment becomes better suited for vectors and transmission of MBDs, dengue-fever risk areas have been expanding in recent years and even resurfaced in places where dengue had been eliminated (Leedale et al., 2016). Due to the variety of aetiologies and the distinct nature of

each mosquito-borne pathogen, it is difficult to model all the factors influencing the transmission of MBDs. *Figure*, above, illustrates the complexity of dengue transmission cycles as shaped by a range of meteorological, environmental, epidemiological and social determinants (WHO, 2012; Ebi & Nealon, 2016).

Prevention and Control

Integrated Vector Management

The WHO (2009) promotes vector control strategies through Integrated Vector Management (IVM). IVM involves strategic decision-making to maximize the effectiveness of resources, optimizing their use. There are three main ways to control vectors through IVM: environmental management, chemical control and biological control. Environmental management involves making changes to the environment to manage vector populations and transmission, for example, closing access to water containers for mosquitoes will reduce reproduction rates as these are used as oviposition sites. Chemical control is widely used in malaria and dengue-endemic areas and usually involves the use of pesticides and insecticides targeted at either mosquito larvae, adult mosquitoes, or both. Insecticides have been widely used in the past due to their effectiveness in reducing mosquito populations and have been a key part of many interventions in the fight to eradicate mosquito-borne diseases such as malaria and dengue (Mathenge et al., 2001). Biological control involves introducing organisms that prey upon, compete against, or result in reductions of the target species (WHO, 2009). Thus IVM is a balanced approach aimed at reducing vector populations with strategic use of limited resources mainly through these three direct mechanisms (WHO, 2009).

However, the overuse of insecticides to control mosquito populations has resulted in a growing number of cases of insecticide resistance among mosquito populations in areas associated with their intensive use (Hemingway, Hawkes, McCarrol, & Ranson, 2004). Insecticide resistance is understood as a genetic heritable trait of insects reducing their susceptibility to insecticides (Hemingway, Hawkes, McCarrol, & Ranson, 2004). Different mechanisms of resistance have been identified. Metabolic resistance usually involves alterations in genetic information resulting in changes in the activity of detoxification proteins (Lines, Myamba & Curtis, 1987). Behavioural mechanisms however result in

alterations in the target's behaviour. For example, the use of Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT) and permethrin, which are mostly used indoors, have resulted in changes in the frequency of mosquitoes entering houses (Mathenge et al., 2001).

The use of insecticides has proved effective in controlling mosquito and larvae numbers in the short-term through a variety of applications. Some of these include indoor and outdoor spraying, using larvicides in stagnant bodies of water, utilizing insecticide-treated nets (ITNs) in MBDs endemic areas as well as repellent spraying. As such, insecticides remain a key tool in the WHO's *Global Vector Control Response 2017-2030* (GVCR). However, concerns about the negative impacts arising from the misuse and overuse of insecticides remain. Adverse ecosystem impacts are concerning risks associated with intensive insecticide and larvicide practices as chemical agents may result in the death of non-target species in an ecosystem. These include pollinator species that are crucial to ecosystem health and human health. Particularly, this is problematic if the insecticiding practices kill natural mosquito predators in the ecosystem, creating a bigger dependence on chemical control. Moreover, predator populations take longer to recover, which can lead to booms in mosquito populations if resistance develops in the area or if insecticidal practices are scaled down (Papchenkova & Makrushin, 2013; Su et al., 2019).

Likewise worrying is the adverse impact insecticides have on human health. Numerous studies show that common pesticide compounds used to control mosquito populations such as organophosphorus and pyrethroid have been associated with delayed neurological prenatal development as well as male reproductive health. In adults, exposure to insecticides has been linked to DNA damage, detrimental neurologic effects, and worsening birth outcomes (Koureas, Tsakalof, Tsatsakis, & Hadjichristodoulou, 2012). Efforts to develop new insecticides such as neonicotinoids to replace more toxic compounds have so far failed to produce safe alternatives. For instance, chronic exposure to neonicotinoids has been associated with birth defects, DNA damage as well as cardiovascular and neurological symptoms (Thompson et al., 2020). It is estimated that insecticide poisoning affects 26 million people leading to 220,000 deaths globally. Moreover, with 36% of the global workforce exposed to insecticides regularly through employment in agriculture, insecticides have become a serious risk to human health worldwide, highlighting the need to

decrease our dependence on insecticides to control mosquito populations (Ansari, Moraiet, & Ahmad, 2014).

Innovations: Vaccines and Wolbachia Bacterium

Along with the spread of MBDs, have come novel strategies to control and prevent their spread, most notably the development of vaccines such as RTS, S/AS01 for malaria, and the 17D vaccine against yellow fever (CDC, 2023). Vaccines have become effective tools in reducing the mortality of mosquito-borne diseases and are part of different strategies to fight MBDs around the world. This has become part of recommendations for interventions and travel by the WHO (WHO, 2023) and Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2021b). However, while vaccines offer protection against infections and dangerous symptoms associated with different pathogens, on their own they fail to address the underlying factors fuelling the spread of MBDs, such as lack of water sanitation, increased contact with natural ecosystems through urbanisation into forested areas, ecosystems and biodiversity loss, and climate change among others.

In addition, advances in research have led to new uses for *Wolbachia*, a bacterium naturally present in about 60% of insects, In *Aedes aegypti* mosquitoes, *Wolbachia* reduces the transmissibility of MBDs including dengue, Zika, and chikungunya. In practice, *Wolbachia*, which is safe for humans and animals alike, is injected into male mosquitoes, and following their release into natural settings, these mate with the wild mosquito population. If the female mosquito is not infected with *Wolbachia*, she will lay eggs that will not hatch, however, if the female mosquito is infected, the offspring she will produce will be born with the bacterium, which will be passed on to future generations (CDC, 2022). While this method of prevention seems promising, research is still ongoing to assess potential unknown adverse outcomes. Concerns about negative impacts on mosquito populations which are a vital keystone species of many ecosystems around the world remain. Additionally, this costly strategy may be prohibitive in low-resource areas, where mosquito-borne diseases are the most prevalent (CDC, 2022). Lastly, over time targeted mosquitoes are at risk of developing anti-microbial resistance (AMR) to *Wolbachia* reducing the effectiveness of this intervention (CDC, 2022).

Given the urgency of addressing VBDs and the climate crisis, interventions protecting and preserving natural habitats of known mosquito predators are key aspects of nature-based solutions to reduce the burden of MBDs. Hence, policies aimed at reducing the burden of MBDs could benefit from efforts aimed at preserving predators' habitats and ecosystem services as part of sustainable vector management strategies.

A Nature-Based Solution against MBDs

Given the challenges and concerns arising from climate change among others, the importance of nature-based solutions (NBS) is more present than ever. According to the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN), nature-based solutions are actions addressing societal challenges while protecting, sustainably managing, and restoring natural ecosystems in a manner that benefits people, diversity, and the environment. Nature-based solutions address a range of current challenges including climate change, loss of biodiversity, water and food security, and health among others, and play a critical role in achieving sustainable development (IUCN, 2023).

NBS as a response to the disadvantages of relying heavily on insecticides have been gaining attention in recent years. Environmental management involves making changes to the environment to reduce mosquito propagation and their contact with humans. This can include changes such as environmental modification like the installation of pipes and mosquito-proofing water containers to reduce access to larval habitats. The effectiveness of these interventions is well supported by literature and past successes in the reduction of MBDs (MSF, 2022).

Over recent years a growing number of studies have been published investigating the potential use of mosquito and larval predators in controlling vector populations. Additionally, apart from the direct mechanisms resulting in reductions in mosquito populations, larval predation stress has been associated with stunted growth and decreased longevity in adult mosquitoes, as well as lower fecundity rates (Costanzo, Muturi, & Alto, 2011; Van Uitregt, Hurst, & Wilson, 2012). Although others do report significant results, it has proven difficult to replicate laboratory findings in real-life settings (WHO, 2009). Researchers report that the unpredictable relationship between the introduction of predators and mosquito numbers may be the result of complex interactions with environmental factors (Roux & Robert, 2019).

Moreover, literature about the topic seems to be scattered due to the different use of terminology, methodology, species of mosquitoes and predators, and outcome measurements. These make many studies hard to find, analyse, compile, and compare, and thus, there is a need to compile these multidisciplinary findings to ease their usability for interventions and future research.

Objectives and Research Questions

Thus, this study seeks to bridge the existing literature on the topic by compiling numerous studies to provide an overview of the general progress and to explore the relevant academic landscape of literature on using predators of mosquitoes and their larvae to address the spread of MBDs. The following review will attempt to shed some light and organize perspectives, facets and the nature of an under-researched topic to organise a broad range of studies with a variety of foci and methodologies as well as the challenges to implementing these solutions in the fight against MBDs. The present study will seek to answer the following research questions:

(1) What is the current state of research on the role and use of predators of mosquitoes and their larvae to control mosquito-borne diseases?

(2) What are the challenges and opportunities of the use of predators of mosquitoes and their larvae to control mosquito-borne diseases identified in the literature?

Scientific and Societal Relevance

This review will be important to get a better overview of the different aspects of predation of mosquitoes and their larvae, and the possible mechanisms through which predators could impact in control of mosquitoes and MBDs. Additionally, this scoping review may provide a useful platform from which future research and interventions may be contextualized, by providing an overview of potentially useful predators and factors affecting their effectiveness. Further, the findings may be used to guide future policy decisions regarding the control of mosquito-borne diseases. As there does not appear to have been scoping reviews on this specific subject at the time of writing this paper will present an important approach to studying nature-based solutions to MBDs.

Methodology

A scoping review was carried out between January to August of 2023 to investigate the current state of research on the use of predators against mosquitoes and their larvae for the control of MBDs. To carry out this scoping review, a protocol was drafted using the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) Checklist (Tricco et al., 2018). Items in the PRISMA-ScR checklist are presented below (*Table 2*).

Table 2:

PRISMA-ScR checklist - Methods Section (Tricco et al., 2018).

Methods	
Protocol and registration	Indicate whether a review protocol exists; state if and where it can be accessed (e.g., a Web address); and provide registration information, including the registration number if available.
Eligibility criteria	Specify characteristics of the sources of evidence used as eligibility criteria (e.g., years considered, language, and publication status), and provide a rationale.
Information sources	Describe all information sources in the search (e.g., databases with dates of coverage and contact with authors to identify additional sources), as well as the date the most recent search was executed.
Search strategy	Present the full electronic search strategy for at least one database, including any limits used, such that it could be repeated.
Selection of sources of evidence	State the process for selecting sources of evidence (i.e., screening and eligibility) included in the scoping review.
Data charting process	Describe the methods of charting data from the included sources of evidence (e.g., calibrated forms or forms that have been tested by the team before their use, and whether data charting was done independently or in duplicate) and any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators.

Data items	List and define all variables for which data were sought and any assumptions and simplifications made.
Critical appraisal of individual sources of evidence	If done, provide a rationale for conducting a critical appraisal of included sources of evidence; describe the methods used and how this information was used in any data synthesis (if appropriate).
Synthesis of results	Describe the methods of handling and summarizing the data that were charted.

It is important to note that the optional item “Critical appraisal of individual sources of evidence” is not relevant to this review as the goal of the present study is to provide an overview of the state of research regarding the use of predators of mosquitoes and their larvae as a tool to address MBDs. Additionally, the items “information sources” and “search strategy” are presented together as they are related.

Protocol and Registration

A new scoping review protocol was created for this study since there was no pre-existing protocol at the time of writing. The present protocol will not be registered due to time constraints related to the nature of this thesis. The literature search process took place between June and July of 2023.

Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion criteria in this scoping review included empirical studies investigating biological control of mosquito populations, or the use of mosquito/larval predators to control MBDs. As such, studies investigating changes in mosquito population densities, mosquito size, population size, or biting/feeding behaviours were included in the review. There was no limitation for publication years of the sources to explore the historical research context on biological control. No publications were discarded based on geographical origin either, as MBDs are a global issue and mosquitoes are present in every continent. Studies and publications must be written in English to be included, meaning that studies in other languages were excluded from the review due to the scarcity of time and resources for the translation of sources. Studies and publications investigating diseases associated with other

vectors outside of mosquitoes, such as ticks or flies were excluded from this scoping review. Lastly, sources for which the full text was not available were excluded from the final selection of sources.

Information sources & search strategy

To identify potential sources for the scoping review, databases that contain relevant publications in the field of MBDs were searched. These databases include SCOPUS, PubMed and the Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews (CDSR). For the search strategy, the following search terms and Boolean operators were used for each database:

- SCOPUS - "Biological control" AND mosquitoes OR larvae AND predators
- PubMed - Mosquito Predators OR Larval Predators AND Biological control
- CDSR - Mosquito predator OR Larval predators OR Biological control of Mosquitoes

Multiple combinations of search terms were tried with each database to try and capture as many relevant sources in the search as possible.

Selection of sources of evidence

As this review is part of a Master's thesis project of a student from Maastricht University, the selection of sources of evidence was carried out by a single researcher. After searching each database using the search strategy mentioned above, sources that were published in a language different from English were removed. A title screening followed and the abstracts of titles that were not clear for the inclusion or exclusion of the sources were examined. Duplicates were removed at this stage, followed by a deeper analysis of the sources which resulted in the exclusion of those considered to be out of scope. Lastly, while proceeding to analyse the remaining pool of sources, studies that were not accessible through the Maastricht University Library or public means were excluded from the final sample of this scoping review.

Data charting process and extraction of data items

The following form was developed based on JBI's Manual for Evidence Synthesis (2022), although some items were adapted to fit this review's design to extract and chart

individual sources of information. Selected sources were charted on a Microsoft Excel document where they were organized in a table charting important information including as shown in the list below: Source characteristics:

- a) Title
 - b) Author(s)
 - c) Publication year
 - d) Publisher
 - e) Continent of origin
 - f) Nature of study (controlled trial, observation, review)
 - g) The setting of the study
 - h) Life-stage of target prey (eggs, larvae, pupae, adult mosquito)
 - i) Predator species studied
 - j) Outcome measures (if applicable)
 - k) Key findings
- 1) Findings about challenges and limitations of using mosquito/larval predators to control MBDs
 - a) Practical challenges
 - b) Environmental implications
 - c) Human health implications

Results

Study Selection

After searching the three databases using the search terms mentioned in the methods section, 2375 sources were identified. The SCOPUS search produced the most number of potential sources (n = 1751), followed by PubMed (n = 560), and Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews (CDSR), which produced 64 potential sources. CSV files were downloaded with key information from each source including titles, authors, language of publication, the database from which the source was acquired, publication ID, and the year of publication. Additionally, some databases provided an abstract and a URL. CSV files were converted into Microsoft Excel Macro-Enabled Worksheets (.xlsm) and merged into a single file.

The first level of screening began by removing all sources that were not in English (n = 81); followed by a title screening, and followed in turn by an abstract screening, which resulted in the removal of 2016 sources from the collection of databases; from the remaining sources, duplicates were removed (n = 108). The remaining sources were given a local ID number to aid with further screening, identification and analysis. After these first rounds of screening, the second round assessed 170 sources for eligibility. From this subset (n = 170), 18 more sources were considered to be out of scope and removed after deeper analysis. Lastly, lack of access through the Maastricht University Library or public means resulted in the further removal of 60 sources. Thus, after both rounds of screening 92 sources were included in the review out of the 2375 originally identified. This information is summarized in the flow diagram below.

Figure 2:

Flow diagram showcasing the data collection and the screening process.

PRISMA 2020 flow diagram for updated systematic reviews which included searches of databases and registers only

Study characteristics

Publication years

From the 92 sources examined, the oldest source included was from 1963, while the newest at the time of writing was from 2023. However, due to a lack of access during the last screening round, most sources included tend to be rather new. This is because the older the study is, the chances that it was publicly available, or accessible through the Maastricht University Library, were also lower.

Figure 3:

The number of publications on using predators for the control of mosquitoes and their larvae per year.

Geographical location

The studies were carried out in a range of different countries, and categorized by continent. Results showed that in the sample (N = 92), 12 (13%) were published by African institutions; 34 (37%) by Asian institutions; eight (8.7%) came from European organizations; 17 (18.5%) originated in North America; nine (9.8%) in South America; 11 (12%) came from Oceania; and one (1.1%) source came from international institutions, namely the WHO (*Figure 4*).

Figure 4:

Location of study publication by continent.

Source Journals

The total sample of sources contained publications from 42 different journals (See *Figure 5 in Appendix A*). The sources were spread evenly, with the exception of *The Journal of the American Mosquito Control Association* which accounted for 16 out of the 92 publications (17.4%), the *Journal of Vector Ecology* with eight (8.7%) sources; *Medical and Veterinary Entomology* with seven (7.6%); and the *Journal of Medical Entomology* with six (6.5%) publications.

The sample of sources was further grouped into different disciplines based on the focus of each journal (*Figure 6*). Health and medicine (n = 48) was the scientific discipline with the most publications, followed by ecology (n = 35). Furthermore, eight journals were multidisciplinary, meaning they do not have a particular focus, or specialize in an intersection of a few disciplines. Lastly, there was one source in the sample from an agricultural journal (also see *Table 3* in *Appendix B*).

Figure 6:

Discipline focus of publisher.

Study designs

Out of the sources analysed, 69 (75%) of those involved controlled trials; 14 (15%) included naturalistic observations, such as ecosystem surveys of water sources, and oviposition sites; lastly, 11 (10%) studies were literary or systematic reviews. Two sources

used mixed methods, one including both a controlled trial and naturalistic observations, and one including a controlled trial alongside a review of available evidence.

This review included studies performed in both natural (n = 32) and laboratory (n = 64) settings, reviews of different types are not included in this statistic. Interestingly, one study was a model-based simulation carried out in a virtual environment. Most controlled trials took place in laboratory conditions and allowed researchers to compare methods, under different situations. A high number of control trials suggest that researchers have used a range of different methodologies to test for different interventions.

Mosquito species

The genera of mosquitoes (and their larvae) preyed upon were also recorded. 41 sources studied *Aedes* (Diptera: Culicidae) mosquitoes; 27 *Culex* (Diptera: Culicidae); 19 *Anopheles* (Diptera: Culicidae); four sources looked at other species including, such as *Culiseta longiareolata*; and 12 studies did not focus on any single mosquito genera in particular.

Mosquito life-cycle stages

The life stage of the mosquito life cycle was also identified for each source. This was done to investigate which stages of the mosquito's life cycle are the most common target of interventions. In the sample, the life stage that received the most attention was larvae, which accounted for 72 sources, one source investigated pupae; adult mosquitoes were researched by four; and 11 sources focused on multiple stages of the mosquito life cycle. Sources that focused on multiple stages were different types of reviews, controlled trials with different foci, or observations measuring mosquito population densities as an outcome variable without a clear stage as the target for intervention.

Disease foci

During the preliminary analysis, the disease focus of each source was determined. This was recorded to find out whether certain MBDs attract more attention from researchers and explore the nature and context of the sources. While most sources (n = 56) did not make any mention of diseases; nine focused on malaria; 11 on dengue; one on yellow fever; and

16 sources mentioned MBDs or vector-borne diseases in general without a focus on any particular one of them.

Predators

A list of the mosquito predators analysed in the review is provided below (Table 4). Notably, the most common taxa of predators in the sample of literature are different species of fish (n = 28), copepods (n = 25), mosquitoes of the genus *Toxorhynchites* (n = 9), and dragonflies (n = 8), which are all species living in or in the proximity of freshwater sources. Predators have been listed in order by frequency of appearance in the literature analysed.

Figure 7:

Distribution of predator appearance in the sample of sources.

Fish

Out of the 28 publications studying mosquito predation different species of freshwater fish were observed, including *Gambusia affinis* (Mosquitofish), *Gila Orcutt* (Arroyo chub), *Poecilia reticulata* (Guppy), *Pimephales promelas* (Fathead minnow), *Aphyosemion gularis* (Annual killifish), *Hyseleotris galii* (Australian mangrove fish), *Pseudogobius sp.* (Australian mangrove fish), *Misgurnus mizolepis* (Dojo loach), *Puntius tetrazona* (Tiger barb), and *Hyphessobrycon rosaceus* (Rosy tetra). The majority of the sources investigated larvivorous fish, which prey on larvae (n = 19), Partially, success during interventions may be determined by the predator's preference between different mosquito species, for example, Alison and Cech (1990) observed apparent preferences between different *Culex* larvae breeds by mosquitofish. Barik et al. (2018), found that there were differences in predatory efficiency between species of *Astyanax fasciatus*, commonly known as the Mexican Tetra, *Trichogaster trichopterus*, also known as the Three-spot Gourami and *Poecilia sphenops* (Barik, et al., 2018). While Barik et al. (2018), found the first two species showed little differences between sexes and exhibited high larvicidal efficiency, only *Poecilia sphenops* females proved effective in laboratory conditions. In general, 19 sources had significant findings for the use of different species of fish for the control of mosquitoes.

Copepods

Copepods (*Copepoda*) are small crustaceans common in both marine and freshwater sources, and according to the sources examined, play an important role in regulating the population of mosquitoes, by feeding on their larvae. In this sample, 20 studies supported the use of different species of copepods for the biological control of mosquitoes (Brown, et al., 1996; Cuthbert, Callaghan & Dick, 2019; Dieng et al., 2002...). In large studies, carried out in natural settings in rural and urban areas, copepods were found to significantly larvae populations in Vietnam, Australia and Sri Lanka (Brown, et al., 1996; Nam, et al., 2000; Udayanga et al., 2019), suggesting they have a strong potential to be incorporated in integrated community-based interventions against MBDs (Nam, et al., 2000).

Key to the potential copepods provide for biological control in long-term strategies lies in their high survivability and low maintenance needs (Marti et al., 2004). In controlled environments, copepods have managed to survive for over 100 days without mosquitoes as a source of food (Marti et al., 2004), highlighting the low resources needed to maintain them. Further, it was found that copepods may survive the seasonal population declines of mosquitoes. According to Dieng et al. (2003), survival rates, and thus, chances of success can be increased by releasing, abundant, and commonly available paramecia as a food source upon early introduction to a new environment, improving the probability of colonization. Additionally, Rey *et al.* (2004) concluded that copepods' low maintenance and ease of culture further benefited from the relative simplicity and inexpensiveness of delivery to target areas during interventions. Given the extensive research carried out using this mosquito predator, numerous factors affecting predation rates, efficiency, strengths and challenges have been identified.

Temperature is an environmental factor associated with predatory success. Copepods in South America, tend to thrive better in temperatures of 26°C than 16°C, translating into higher survival rates, and predatory efficacy (Calliari, et al., 2003). Brown and colleagues (1996), determined that due to its specific temperature tolerance, *M. aspericornis* failed to bring consistent reductions in mosquito larvae control during the colder Brisbane winters. These findings highlight the importance of matching predator species with local habitats and their conditions to maximize the chances of success of an intervention. Thus, while based on literature, copepods have an impressive record for biological control, their chances of success are also determined by environmental factors and they may not be the best candidate for every intervention. Lastly, these crustaceans share common habitat needs as mosquitoes and provide an opportunity to substitute the use of insecticides with a cheaper, environmentally friendlier alternative, which may prove particularly useful in hard-to-reach breeding sites such as mines and wells (Russel, Muir, Weinstein, & Kay, 1996).

Different copepod species also provide different effectiveness. However, this may be also mediated by other factors such as environmental (Russell, Qureshi, Wilson, & Cator, 2021; Udayanga, et al., 2019) or prey characteristics. Panogadia-Reyes, Cruz & Bautista (2004) found that in terms of predation rates of larval dengue vectors, *M. aspericornis* and

M. ogunnus differed significantly. However, mixing different species of copepods for example can result in stunted growth and decreased survival rates (Dieng, et al., 2002). Additionally, while copepods are not dangerously pathogenic to humans, the use of these copepods in drinking water is not recommended (Rawlins, et al., 1997).

***Toxorhynchites* mosquitoes**

Toxorhynchites is a genus of mosquitoes that has received increasing attention in research and practice as a potential source of biological control of mosquito vectors of disease. *Toxorhynchites* mosquitoes in contrast to blood-feeding mosquitoes, mostly feed on plant juices such as nectar, making them safe for humans. Their larvae, on the other hand, predate other mosquito larvae including dengue vector *Aedes* (Zuharah et al., 2015), Malaria vector *Anopheles* (Zuharah et al., 2015), Japanese Encephalitis and West Nile Virus vector *Culex* mosquitoes (Brown et al., 1996). While most studies support the use of *Toxorhynchites* in integrated biological control programs (Brown, et al., 1996; Focks, 2007; Nyamah, Sulaiman, & Omar, 2011...), some studies report mixed results (Kesavaraju & Juliano, 2004; Schreiber, 2007), and highlight key factors associated with their use that could determine their success in real life applications. For example, a 22-month-long naturalistic field survey of tires, a common breeding site for *Aedes* and *Culex* mosquitoes in Australia, found 90.70% fewer larvae per litre in tires where *Tx. speciosu* (*Toxorhynchites*), were present (4 larvae/litre and 43 larvae/litre, respectively) (Brown, et al., 1996). These results were consistent throughout the entirety of the survey (Brown, et al., 1996). Due to other predators and competing prey *Toxorhynchites*' prospects may, however, be most effective in restricted environments such as isolated islands (Schreiber, 2007), or water-storage containers (Focks, 2007). These mosquitoes may not be as effective in large bodies of water, where prey larvae density is low, in comparison with smaller, high larval density environments (Schreiber, 2007). The latter may be more effective for tackling outbreaks of MBDs as it is a controllable environment. The ability and capacity to control aspects of the intervention such as water temperature, or the site where the mosquitoes will be introduced is important for the sustainability and long-term self-sufficiency of the intervention. In laboratory settings in Africa, *Tx. brevialpis* successfully colonized water containers at 25°C in the presence of *Ae. aegypti* (Trpis & Gerberg, 1993).

Dragonflies

All sources in the sample studying dragonflies were carried out in Africa or Asia. Species of dragonflies mentioned in the examined sources include *Brachytron pratense* (hairy dragonfly) and *Aeshnidae odonate* (darners) dragonflies. Out of the eight studies in the sample, seven investigating predatory efficiency, concluded that dragonfly nymphs could be used for biological control of mosquitoes in an integrated approach (Chatterjee, Ghosh, & Chandra, 2007; Eba, et al., 2021; Khan, et al., 2022; Mandal, Ghosh, Bhattacharjee, & Chandra, 2008; Murugan, et al., 2015; Samanmali, et al., 2018). It appears that nymphs may not be fit to change the oviposition behaviour of mosquitoes in significant ways (Stav, Blaustein, & Margalit, 2000), however, more research is necessary to find out the real impact these insects may have on egg deposition behaviours. According to Eba et al. (2021), dragonflies provide high predatory efficacy rates, and given how common they are in urban areas, provide a potential use for biological control of mosquitoes in cosmopolitan areas. Predation rates differ per species, but there is a wide range of nymphs that seem promising for interventions in different contexts. For example, Samanmali, et al. (2018), report that while *Anax indicus* is by far the most aggressive dragonfly against *Aedes* larvae in Sri Lanka, *P.flavescen*'s wide geographical range and notable predation may provide a strong ecosystem service on the island. Additionally, studies in natural settings also report that odonate nymphs offer a good option for biological control in temporary pools and large aquatic habitats, given their ability to control mosquito larvae (Mandal, Ghosh, Bhattacharjee, & Chandra, 2008).

Backswimmers

All five studies investigating the use of backswimmers (Notonectid Bug) supported their potential as a biological control agent (Eba, et al., 2021; Eitam & Blaustein, 2004; Shaalan, et al., 2007; Wattal, Adak, Dhiman, & Sharma, 1996; Zuharah, Fadzly & Lester, 2013). Furthermore, backswimmers were reported to be the most aggressive predator against *Anopheles* mosquito larvae - more aggressive than dragonflies (Odonata), true bugs (Hemiptera), and flies (Diptera) (Eba et al., 2021). Additionally, according to Zuharah *et al.* (2013), chemical residuals left by backswimmers in mosquito breeding sites have sublethal effects on mosquito populations, including a decrease in the amounts of total eggs hatched. Researchers believe the lower egg-hatching rates are affected by stress mechanisms and

epigenetic processes. Backswimmers seem to be effective predators against *Anopheles*, *Culex*, and *Aedes* mosquitoes giving them wide effectiveness against a variety of MBDs vectors, and suggesting different species of backswimmers may be effective across wide geographical areas (Eba et al., 2021; Eitam & Blaustein, 2004; Zuharah, et al., 2013).

Heteropteran

There were two studies investigating Heteropteran insects, commonly known as true bugs, in this review. Both studies, carried out in naturalistic settings, concluded that Heteropteran insects can be a successful biological control agent (Ohba, et al., 2011; Shaalan, et al., 2007). Shaalan *et al.* (2011), report that true bug species (*Diplonychus sp.*) was more successful in reducing *Culex* mosquito populations in Australia than copepods. (*Anisops sp.*), during a twelve-month survey. In Vietnam, a survey of water jars and containers used to store water for daily life, and known mosquito breeding sites, found that Heteropterans corixidae (*Micronecta spp.*) and veliidae (*Microvelia spp.*) were commonly found and are dominant predators of *Aedes* mosquitoes inside this closed environments (Ohba, et al., 2011). More research is needed to determine the exact potential of true bugs in the context of biological control, but based on the research included in this review, sources reported that Heteropteran insects can be good candidates for biological control in integrated interventions, and already provide an invaluable ecosystem service as natural regulators of mosquito populations.

Flies

The two sources studying flies (Diptera), tried to investigate the future predation rates under climate change. Thus, while it is difficult to assess their current potential from this data, both studies assume flies are successful and important predators of mosquitoes. Tran, et al. (2016) conclude that under current warming trends, to preserve effective predation rates against mosquitoes, high-latitude flies will have to evolve toward low-latitude characteristics, or the low-latitude Diptera will have to expand northward.

Spiders

One study in this sample studied the predatory potential of East African jumping spiders (*Salticidae*) for the control of malaria vector, *Anopheles* mosquitoes in adulthood

(Nelson & Jackson, 2006). In the study investigating predatory preferences and behaviours, researchers concluded that the East African jumping spider, prefers to feed on female mosquitoes, which carry vertebrate blood after feeding. This spider can identify *Anopheles* mosquitoes by sight, and lure them by positioning other insect carcasses in life-like postures. Among *Anopheles*, only female mosquitoes feed on blood, and thus they are responsible for transmitting MBDs (Nelson & Jackson, 2006). Thus, given its preference for female *Anopheles*, researchers concluded that the East African jumping spider (*Salticidae*) has a predatory preference for the malaria vector *Anopheles* mosquito, and suggest that the use or protection of such spiders may provide ecosystem services in the shape of mosquito control with little risk to other non-malaria carrying insects in the region.

Beetles

Three studies investigating the predatory potential of diving beetles (*Coleoptera: Dytiscidae*) against *Culex* & *Aedes* larvae produced results suggesting high predatory efficiency by these insects. Naturalist observations in Kerala, India, reported reductions of 70.91% and 100% in the larval population of the dengue-carrying *Aedes* mosquito, while they were found to eat 17 (+/-5) larvae per day in laboratory settings (Kumar, et al., 2014). All three studies agree on the importance of preserving the habitats of these Coleopterans given the key roles they play in the natural biological control of different mosquito species (Kumar, et al., 2014; Lundkvist, Landin, Jackson, & Svensson, 2003). Lastly, Banerjee et al. (2008), highlight the potential of the diving beetle for pest and vector control strategies in relationship to medically important species of mosquitoes.

Turtles

Juvenile turtles have long been discussed as potential candidates for biological control. In the sample, only one study investigated turtles' potential for controlling mosquito populations (Marten, 2007). An investigation carried out in both laboratory and natural settings in Honduras, observing juvenile turtles in water-storage tanks to aid dengue interventions, reported a total mosquito elimination from the water tanks. Likewise, the researchers report a decrease of 99% in *Culex quinquefasciatus* mosquitoes in roadside ditches in Louisiana, US (Marten, 2007). While turtles have a high predatory capacity eating

around 500 larvae per day, turtles are hosts to the *Salmonella* bacteria when kept in small enclosures. However, they appear to be safe for humans when kept in large water-storage tanks, and oviposition sites (Marten, 2007). Given the high risk and dangers of infection, further research is necessary to safely utilize turtles for biological control in drinking water sources. Turtles have more potential for mosquito control in natural habitats, or non-potable aquatic sites in rural and urban areas (Marten, 2007).

Tadpoles

Among the examined sources, there was a single study investigating the potential of frogs for mosquito control (Willems, Webb & Russell, 2005). This study reported that tadpoles had only a minor impact on the control of *Culex* mosquitoes, suggesting that frogs may only have a limited impact on mosquito control. However, while the direct impact of predation was limited in this study, the researchers suggest that tadpoles may have indirect effects on mosquito populations that may help reduce mosquito populations through competition mechanism, as the presence of tadpoles has been associated with decreases in pupal size, growth, survival rates, and development. More studies are necessary to understand under which conditions tadpoles and frogs may be most effective in biological control strategies (Willems, Webb & Russell, 2005).

Flatworms

A single study carried out in laboratory settings found different flatworm species (*Girardia anceps*, *Mesostoma ehrenbergii* and *Bothrosostoma cf. evelinae*), to reduce larval populations of *Aedes* and *Culex* mosquitoes by 52% to 100%, in permanent water containers, and temporary puddles (Tranchida, et al., 2009). The highest larvicidal potential occurred in closed environments, leading the researchers of this study to conclude that flatworms may be the most effective in inoculated environments.

Shrimps

There was a single study within the sample investigating the use of the freshwater shrimp *Macrobrachium tenellum* against *Aedes* larvae in a controlled trial under laboratory conditions (Rojas-Sahagún, et al., 2012). The adaptability of this species makes it a strong

candidate for biological control of mosquitoes. *Macrobrachium tenellum* is found in large numbers and is known to withstand a wide range of temperatures, oxygen concentrations and salinity levels (Rojas-Sahagún, et al., 2012). Rojas-Sahagún *et al.* (2012), found *Macrobrachium tenellum* to reduce mosquito larval populations by 95% in containers with small shrimp (3-3.5cm), and 100% in those with slightly bigger ones (4-4.5cm). The characteristics mentioned above in addition to their voracity against mosquito larvae, give *Macrobrachium tenellum* a high potential role as a biocontrol agents across different regions and climates, in the presence of climate change.

Plants

The Bladderwort plant *Utricularia vulgaris* (Lentibulariaceae), is a carnivorous plant native to tropical or temperate regions. Bladderworts can be both terrestrial or aquatic, and while it is not the only type of carnivorous plants, the sample of this review contained one study investigating these plants' potential for mosquito control through controlled trials in both natural and laboratory settings (Baumgartner, 1987). The study concludes that bladderworts are an efficient biological agent against mosquitoes in controlled closed environments. During their trials under laboratory conditions, the aquatic plants managed to reduce *Culex* mosquito larval populations by 50% in three days. Under field conditions however, it was concluded that these plants would not be effective biological control interventions on their own, as their predation rates on mosquito larvae dropped significantly, probably due to competing prey (Baumgartner, 1987). One problematic aspect of using bladderwort plants as long-term, self-sustaining interventions, is that their inability to catch mosquito pupae can lead to stunted growth of these plants during early summer (in Illinois, US). Because of their seasonal life cycle, *U. vulgaris* may prove ineffective against spring and fall mosquito species (Baumgartner, 1987). Lastly, their spatial limitation to permanent freshwater sources makes them effective for *Culex* control but reduces their usefulness against so-called floodwater mosquitoes (breeds at temporary water sites, such as puddles) such as *Aedes* (Baumgartner, 1987). Hence, decisions for biological control interventions using *Utricularia vulgaris* should be determined by environmental and prey specifications and must be tailored for each target site (Baumgartner, 1987).

Geckoes

There was one study in the sample with geckoes. Canyon and Hii (1997), studied the diet preferences and predatory capacity of two gecko species, the Australian gecko (*Gehyra dubia*) and the Asian house gecko (*Hemidactylus frenatus*) under laboratory conditions. In their study, *Culex*, *Aedes* and *Anopheles* who had either been freshly fed on blood, unfed, or were carrying eggs (gravid), were placed in a terrarium with the geckoes. The researchers found that both geckoes fed significantly more on gravid mosquitoes than the other two groups.

Salamanders

One study investigated Tiger salamanders (*Ambystoma tigrinum*) in the sample. Researchers studied the preferences of the tiger salamander and found that under laboratory conditions, tiger salamanders ate 144 mosquito larvae and pupae per day on average, making them the third most common component found in their stomachs (Brodman & Dorton, 2006).

Secondary Control Mechanisms of Predation

While the direct effects of predation have been well understood, mainly as a decrease in target populations, predation also affects prey species through indirect mechanisms that have an impact on predator/ prey interactions.

Oviposition behaviour

In addition to reducing the number of adult mosquitoes, the presence of predators in the breeding sites might affect oviposition behaviours in different ways. Several studies have produced evidence indicating that mosquitoes are less likely to choose predator-infested locations for egg deposition (Dieng, et al., 2017; Louca, et al., 2014; Zuharah, Fadzly & Lester, 2013). In addition, the percentage of final eggs that hatch tends to be lower in areas where predators are present. This was observed with the use of different predators including fish, cannibalistic mosquitoes (*Toxorhynchites*), backswimmers, and dragonflies, among others, and backed by both laboratory and naturalistic sources. The literature suggests that through epigenetic mechanisms, as well as predatory stress, the danger of being preyed upon

has a negative effect on mosquito populations (Dieng, et al., 2017; Louca, et al., 2014; Why, Lara & Walton, 2016; Zuharah, Fadzly & Lester, 2013).

Predator cues and residuals

Cues and residuals indicating the presence of predators to mosquitoes have different effects on mosquito populations. Residual cues also reduce the number of eggs hatching by the real presence of predators, or their cues (Zuharah, Fadzly & Lester, 2013). In addition to chemical residual cues, and brief exposure, oviposition behaviour, is also affected by the presence of literal images of predators in the oviposition sites. For example, Dieng, et al. (2017) reported lower oviposition rates by *Aedes aegypti* in containers with images of fish in them, as compared to blank cups. The study observed similar egg deposition rates independent of the size of the picture, and it provided evidence for a novel, inexpensive, low-maintenance strategy to reduce the presence of mosquitoes in small controlled environments.

These interactions may be dependent on the type of predator used. While supporting evidence has been found for residuals of backswimmers and fish (Zuharah, Fadzly & Lester, 2013; Dieng, et al., 2017), cues indicating the presence of *Toxorhynchites* have so far not provided evidence that it could be used for vector control (Kesavaraju & Juliano, 2004). Similarly, studies investigating the effects of larvivorous fish cues have also failed to replicate significant results (Zuharah, Fadzly & Lester, 2013), suggesting more research needs to be carried out to better understand this interaction and the potential implications for biological control.

Size

Size is an important factor in increasing an individual mosquito's fitness in certain habitats (Kesavaraju & Juliano, 2004). Literature reports that the presence of predators, or predator cues leads to decreases in prey size (van Uiregt, Hurst & Wilson, 2012). This occurs due to predatory preference towards bigger prey, and the increased difficulty of feeding in the presence of predators. Mosquitoes of smaller size, are more likely to experience lower starvation resistance and tend to produce less offspring, decreasing populations of mosquitoes over time (Kesavaraju & Juliano, 2004).

Feeding behaviours

Reduced rates of foraging and feeding have been observed in mosquitoes exposed to predators, to minimize the risk of alerting predatory species (Kesavarju & Juliano, 2004). While it is not yet clear whether this mechanism could lead to a decrease in transmission rates of MBDs, the process could also be species-dependent. In laboratory-controlled trials, *O. triseriatus* reduced feeding rates in the presence of *Toxorhynchites*, while *A. albopictus* did not show significant changes in adapting to low-risk behaviours (Kesavarju & Juliano, 2004). Reductions in foraging behaviours and behavioural adaptations in both adult mosquitoes and their larvae may be key factors influencing size and starvation resistance (Kesavarju & Juliano, 2004; van Uiregt, Hurst & Wilson, 2012).

Starvation resistance

A species' ability to survive for a certain period without food, or starvation resistance, is an important survivalist trait, particularly in environments without a stable source of food (Van Uiregt & Wilson, 2012). In habitats where food sources may be scarce in quantity or difficult to access, due to the presence of predators for example, starvation resistance is an important trait for the survival of that species. Van Uiregt, Hurst & Wilson (2012), found that in laboratory-controlled trials, mosquitoes exhibited lower starvation resistance in the presence of fish. The researchers conclude that the decrease in adult mosquito size, due to predation during the larval stage, may be responsible for the lower tolerance to starvation as smaller mosquitoes have smaller energy reserves (Van Uiregt & Wilson, 2012). Evolutionary impacts could in theory affect future generations of mosquitoes exposed to predators. Lastly, reduced starvation resistance seems to be most impactful against female mosquitoes, for whom body size limits blood consumption, a key source of energy used in egg production (van Uiregt, Hurst & Wilson, 2012).

Challenges

Practical challenges to successful introduction by predators

While the literature on the subject of biological control of mosquitoes is promising, significant challenges to the successful implementation of interventions remain. Ecosystem

dynamics are shaped by a variety of factors and their interactions and introduction of new actors, such as predators, can disrupt certain ecosystem processes resulting in a misbalance in populations of non-target organisms (Adler & Courtney, 2019). Because of this, a lack of deep understanding of ecosystem dynamics can decrease the chances of successful interventions. Additionally, pre-existing chemical control efforts or ill-planned IVM strategies can harm predator populations such as *Toxyrhynchites* (Shaalán & Canyon, 2009). Moreover, extensive knowledge about predator and mosquito biology is necessary in many cases to introduce and maintain a predator species successfully in a new environment. Thus, a lack of knowledge about appropriate practices for the transport and successful colonization of target habitats can easily become a barrier for specific predator-prey-habitat match-ups (Shaalán & Canyon, 2009).

According to Schreiber (2007), climate factors are a key implication to take into account, and thus finding a good match between the predacious species and the habitat where the intervention will take place is a challenge that could determine success or failure. This is particularly challenging in ecosystems with strong seasonal fluctuations, or those exposed to extreme weather events such as El Niño (Schaper, 1999), which endanger the predator feeding and thus long-term sustainability of the intervention. Moreover, due to changing climate conditions in many areas of the world, the suitability and maintenance of certain predators may be affected in certain environments (Brown, et al., 1996; Trpis & Gerberg, 1993). For example, Lundkvist and colleagues (2003) found that due to emigration, researchers did not manage to maintain the population numbers of diving beetles (*Hydroporus spp.*) introduced during the experiment.

The presence of alternative prey for mosquito predators can result in lower efficiency of mosquito control. This is true especially when there is a strong predatory preference for other prey (Alison & Cech, 1990). For example, *Colymbetes paykulli*, another type of beetle, has a preference for *Culex* larvae, while *Ilybius ater* (De Geer) and *I. fuliginosus* (Fabricius) have a preference for common water fleas (*Daphnia*) (Lundkvist, et al., 2003). Mosquito prey species also affect this relationship, with different copepods having preferences for certain prey (Kumar & Ramakrishna, 2003). The presence of alternative prey also led to a reduction in predatory rates among copepods in laboratory trials (Cuthbert, 2018). Interventions using

copepods alone however will not be able to suppress increases in mosquito populations amid rising temperatures (Tuno, Phong & Takagi, 2020). Poliphagy, or the ability of an individual to sustain themselves on multiple sources of food, is a double-edged sword. On one hand, while it provides certain species to survive in the absence of mosquitoes (Shaalan & Canyon, 2009), important in environments where fluctuations in mosquito populations are common, due to seasons for example, it also results in less efficacy of predators due to the presence of alternative prey in their diet (Cuthbert, Callaghan & Dick, 2019).

Ecological and Environmental Implications

Just as with health concerns, biocontrol strategies also have ecological risks and implications. Non-native, invasive species, as well as population booms and busts of certain organisms, can have devastating consequences for an ecosystem (Adler & Courtney, 2019). For example, an invasive species of aquatic fly (chironomid) that predares on mosquitoes, is contributing to the release of great amounts of nitrogen by deepening peat bog depths on Signy Island (Adler & Courtney, 2019). Fly silk commonly found in water sources where these animals are present, has the quality of absorbing pesticides, which helps purify the water from insecticides in integrated vector control strategies. However, as the insecticides are absorbed by the silk, new mechanisms arise for pesticides to enter the food web (Adler & Courtney, 2019).

Human Health

While we use predators to control mosquito populations and improve health outcomes for people, the use of certain animals in some settings may be a health hazard to people in the area of the intervention. Certain types of flies, which are important for mosquito control, and ecosystem food webs in the aquatic environment, are also responsible for transmitting pathogens to humans in their adult stages (Adler & Courtney, 2019). Marten (2007) points out, that while turtles may be excellent candidates for mosquito control in water storage units, they are also hosts of the salmonella bacterium, and thus, in the wrong environment, the use of turtles for biological control could result in new health challenges in communities already affected by MBDs. Other predatory species such as copepods, could also potentially be pathogenic carriers given the right conditions and hence, may not be suitable for interventions

at drinking water sources (Rawlins, et al., 1997). Pathogens, however, are not the only threat biological control poses to human health. Some species of ephydriids (*Hydrellia spp.*), also a predator of mosquito larvae, can negatively impact water-irrigated crops such as rice plantations, posing a risk to food security in world regions depending on rice as a source of food (Adler & Courtney, 2019).

Opportunities

According to the literature, the use of predators of mosquitoes and their larvae has potential as a strategy to address current challenges and concerns associated with intensive insecticide use by using pre-existing ecosystem mechanisms to control mosquito populations (Brown, et al., 1996). Natural observations in Sri Lanka, Vietnam and Australia repeatedly found lower mosquitoes larvae densities or a complete absence of them in breeding sites where predators were present (Brown, et al., 1996; Nam, et al., 2000; Udayanga et al., 2019). Moreover, these control mechanisms currently active, with predators such as freshwater shrimp (*Macrobrachium tenellum*), are already present in natural settings across a wide range of ecosystems globally (Rojas-Sahagún, et al., 2012).

Copepods are reported to be a cheap predator alternative for mosquito control due to their low maintenance needs and simplicity, culture practices and inexpensive transport necessities (Rey, et al., 2004). The potential of certain predators such as *Toxorhynchites* to tackle the impact of MBDs also shows promise, particularly if used as part of integrated vector control programs against dengue, and West Nile Virus vectors, *Aedes* and *Culex* mosquitoes (Nyamah, Sulaiman, & Omar, 2011; Zuharah et al., 2015). Additionally, certain mosquito control agents, such as dragonflies, show high potential to reduce mosquito populations in urban areas, environments with a high human population density (Eba, et al., 2021). Moreover, some predators like the East African jumping spider (*Salticidae*), have a predatory preference for blood-fed mosquitoes, which is an important factor in increasing the likelihood that their prey could be a vector of MBDs (Nelson & Jackson, 2006). Some animal's predatory potential increases in specific environments such as *Toxorhynchites* in restricted islands and water-storage containers (Focks, 2007), and turtles in non-potable aquatic sites like roadside ditches (Marten, 2007).

Discussion

Based on the analysis of available literature, currently, the state of research on the possible role predators can play in the control of mosquitoes and their larvae is still scattered and diverse, arising from a diverse range of scientific disciplines, methodologies and goals, which are not just limited to reducing the burden MBDs place on society. At the same time, this diversity provides a variety of perspectives unsheathing a range of different mechanisms to take into account when refining future interventions. The literature analysis shows that academic interest in mosquito control through the use of predators peaked around 2007 as fewer articles in our sample have been published since then. Part of the decline in the number of publications between 2020 and 2023 could be explained by difficulties posed by the Covid-19 pandemic. Moreover, as the data collection occurred in June and July of 2023, it is likely the final number of publications at the end of the year will be higher than the number provided in this review.

Most research is published by journals dedicated to health medicine and ecology, along the fact that the majority of publications came from Asia could be explained by the high prevalence, morbidity, and mortality MBDs are responsible for in Asian countries (Colón-Gonzalez et al., 2021). Strikingly however, the amount of publications on the biological control of mosquitoes by the use of predators from other regions of the world did not reflect the distribution of the global burden of MBDs, such as in South America and Africa (Colón-Gonzalez et al., 2021). The focus on studying *Aedes*, *Anopheles*, and *Culex* mosquitoes reflects the interest in controlling those mosquito populations responsible for the transmission of the most burdensome MBDs (CDC, 2020; CDC, 2021; WHO, 2019). Using mosquito species to analyse the past and present state of research and its context is perhaps more useful than extrapolating based on disease foci because most sources did not have a particular focus towards a specific disease. Given that most studies focused on the larvae-stage as a target of predation implies two things. First, larvae are the most vulnerable life-stage to predation, perhaps because mosquitoes in their aquatic stages have not developed the ability to fly, making it more difficult to scape predators. The second on the other hand could be a strategic decision to control mosquito populations in their infancy before female adult mosquitoes develop the ability to feed on blood when MBDs are transmitted.

Fish and copepods, followed by *Toxorhynchites* and dragonflies received the most amount of attention in the literature which could suggest that they have the biggest potential for mosquito control. However, no studies compared their effectiveness under similar conditions, making further extrapolations difficult from this review alone. At the same time, the literature shows the importance of a predator's fitness in a specific environment for successful, sustainable interventions. Thus, the literature strongly supports the idea that the choice of predator for a specific setting or environment is a key determinant in achieving reductions of local mosquito populations.

The main barriers to successfully implementing the use of predators as part of wider IVM efforts can be synthesized into three main groups: practical challenges during interventions, ecological and environmental concerns, and risks to human health. However, while these are represented as distinct categories, they are related to one another. To a large extent, some practical difficulties arise from a lack of knowledge of the different multidisciplinary actors and factors, as well as the complex relationships between them. Based on the available literature, risks associated with a lack of knowledge or uninformed decisions in the context of biological control can result in damage to both environmental and human health. For example, apart from the dangers being presented to local fauna and flora by the introduction of predators in an ecosystem, there are also economic risks affecting the broader society associated with booms of certain species, or steep declines in populations of keystone species (Adler & Courtney, 2019).

Due to most studies being carried out in laboratory settings, in the available literature, there is little consideration for the potential impacts the introduction of non-native species can have on local ecosystems. Impacts on non-target species are also notably absent from the sources included. Additionally, while some risks to human health are discussed, an important gap in the literature is the intersection between biological control and human health. Understanding possible interactions between individual predatory species introduced to a new environment is important to reduce the risk increased contact with wildlife could have on human health, in the form of disease outbreaks, for example.

The literature suggests predators are good candidates for mosquito control under specific situations (Rojas-Sahagún, et al., 2012; 1996; Nam, et al., 2000; Udayanga et al.,

2019...). Moreover, under the right conditions, successful interventions can reduce the present dependence IVM has on insecticides (Brown, et al., 1996). While there are risks to human health associated with biological control strategies, diminishing insecticide use can help improve the well-being of those exposed to insecticides. At the same time, more research is necessary to study the relationship between predator use and MBDs, improve our understanding of complex predator-prey dynamics to reduce risks associated with the use of predators for mosquito control and deepen our knowledge of factors that could improve predatory effectiveness and long-term sustainability of interventions, improving chances of success.

Lastly, social acceptability can be boosted by support for sustainable initiatives (Shafique, et al., 2019), suggesting that community acceptance for the use of predators as a mosquito control agent can be improved by educational efforts about sustainability. More research, however, should be directed to assess acceptability across different intervention strategies and educational factors to improve future interventions' community engagement in target areas.

Limitations and Considerations

Due to a lack of access to certain sources, notably absent from the final predator list in the sample of sources were adult frogs and bats, both of whom are well-known mosquito control agents against mosquitoes in both rural and urban areas. Hence, this study could benefit from future adaptations to include a bigger pool of sources, or complementary studies to provide a more complete review of the literature on biological control mosquitoes.

During the data collection, and the screening, access through public means or the university library, tended to favour recently published research over older studies. The lack of older publications in the sample can lead to missing important long-term effects, as more recent research may not have had enough time to evaluate these phenomena. Moreover, this review focused on publications in English, discarding any sources published in other languages due to time, and resource constraints, but it may lead to the underrepresentation of sources from non-English speaking countries. This may explain why Europe has almost as many studies as South America, which is odd given the lower burden of MBDs, and

significantly lower presence of these insects in comparison with tropical, warmer regions. While categorizing locations by continent does provide an overview of where most of the research is produced, continents are big and diverse in mosquito species, and predators and the burden of MBDs varies widely within them. Thus, grouping sources this way may not represent the context of past and current biological control research with nuance. Search strategy bias may arise from the search terms used to scout for sources for each database.

Recommendations Future Research

While there is a substantial amount of research in this field, future interventions using biological control to mitigate the burden of MBDs could benefit from further research. Filling in the gaps in the literature mentioned above will allow for holistic interventions addressing key issues, targets and barriers safely and sustainably. More needs to be understood about the role predatory species could play in controlling mosquito populations in urban areas where most people live, and the potential risks to human health. Individual predator-prey interactions in isolated environments appear to be understood, however, more research is necessary to understand more complicated interactions. Examples include non-target species, competing prey and predators, as well as potential human interactions in real-world settings. Without it, future interventions risk harming native biodiversity, local ecosystems, and human health in the process. However, advances in new research methods including computer modelling, aided by artificial intelligence to produce accurate simulations of the world we live in, have the potential to investigate these aspects safely for ecosystems and biodiversity (Duque, Muñoz & Navarro-Silva, 2004), in addition to cutting costs and waiting times. While computer modelling has its own limitations, it is a tool that may benefit research as a complementation of ongoing efforts and has the potential to speed up knowledge production in the context of biological control. Overall, most research in the sample is discipline-specific, as reflected by the publication data. To effectively combat, MBDs or vector diseases as a whole, future research will have to bridge these pools of field knowledge through multidisciplinary approaches linking ecology, human and planetary health in a One Health approach. Another important focus for future investigations is community acceptability. As different cultures and communities tend to have varied relationships with certain predators of mosquitoes, efforts could be hampered if local communities are not

comfortable with hikes in the population of certain wildlife in their vicinity. Acceptability may also be improved through community engagement and education, as shown by Shafique et al. (2019), but more research is necessary to gain a deeper understanding of the role communities affected by MBDs can play in biological control interventions.

Conclusion

Based on the Literature, the current state of research regarding the use of predators to control mosquito populations is diverse in focus and widely varied in methodologies. The most prominent barriers to integrating predators as biocontrol agents against mosquitoes include (1) practical barriers such as lack of knowledge of complex ecosystem dynamics and climate factors; (2) challenges to the local environment including risks to non-target species and ecosystems; and (3) and risks to human health. To surpass these challenges more interdisciplinary research will be necessary to holistically assess the potential predators that could play in IVM and the impacts it could have on ecosystems, non-target species and human health. Moreover, further research will need to study the impact that biological control by predators of mosquitoes and their larvae could have in reducing the MBDs' prevalence and their burden of disease on society. With a better understanding of these, the most prominent barriers can be addressed. Based on the literature, the use of predatory species as agents in biological control strategies against mosquitoes shows promise as a nature-based solution to tackle MBDs if concerns are appropriately addressed.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Figure 5:

Frequency of publication per publisher.

Appendix B

Table 3:

Frequency of disciplinary focus

Discipline	Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Multi-disciplinary	8	8.7	8.7	8.7
Health & Medicine	48	52.2	52.2	60.9
Ecology	35	38.0	38.0	98.9
Agriculture	1	1.1	1.1	100
Total	92	100	100	

Appendix C

Table 4:

Frequency of mosquito predators in the sample

Predator	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Fish	28	31
Dragonflies	8	9
Copepods	25	28
Spiders	1	1
Beetles	3	4
Mosquitoes	9	10
Turtles	1	1
Tadpoles	1	1
Backswimmers	5	6
Flatworms	1	1
Prawns	1	1
Plants	1	1
Heteropteran Insects	2	2
Lizards	2	2
Flies	2	2

Appendix D

Citation	Title	Journal	Location	Study Design	Setting	Predator	Mosquito Stage	Prey species	Disease
(Abbasi, et al., 2020)	Study on the fauna of aquatic insects in northwestern Iran	Journal of Arthropod-Borne Diseases	Asia	Naturalistic Observation	Naturalistic	Copepods	Larvae	Culicinae	N/A
(Adler & Courtney, 2019)	Ecological and Societal Services of Aquatic Diptera	Insects	North America	Review	N/A	Flies	Multiple Stages	N/A	MBDs
(Barik, et al., 2018)	Larvivorous potentiality of <i>Puntius tetrazona</i> and <i>Hyphessobrycon rosaceus</i> against <i>Culex vishnui</i> subgroup in laboratory and field based bioassay	BMC Research Notes	Asia	Controlled Trial	Both	Fish	Larvae	<i>Culex</i>	MBDs
(Baumgartner, 1987)	Laboratory evaluation of the bladderwort plant, <i>Utricularia vulgaris</i> (Lentibulariaceae), as a predator of late instar <i>Culex pipiens</i> and assessment of its biocontrol potential	Journal of the American Mosquito Control Association	North America	Controlled Trial	Both	Plants	Larvae	<i>Culex</i>	N/A
(Benelli & Mehlhorn, 2016)	Declining malaria, rising of dengue and Zika virus: insights for mosquito vector control	Parasitology Research	Europe	Review	N/A	N/A	Multiple Stages	<i>Aedes</i> , <i>Anopheles</i> , <i>Culex</i>	MBDs

(Bhattacharjee, Aditya & Chandra, 2009)	Laboratory and field assessment of the potential of larvivorous, air-breathing fishes as predators of culicine mosquitoes	Biological Control	Asia	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Fish	Larvae	Culex	N/A
(Blaustein, 1992)	Larvivorous fishes fail to control mosquitoes in experimental rice plots	Hydrobiologia	Asia	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Fish	Larvae	Culex	N/A
(Brodman & Dorton, 2006)	The effectiveness of pond-breeding salamanders as agents of larval mosquito control	Journal of Freshwater Ecology	North America	Naturalistic Observation	Laboratory	Salamander	Larvae	N/A	N/A
(Brown, et al., 1996)	Evaluation of Mesocyclops aspericornis (Cyclopoida:Cyclopidae) and Toxorhynchites speciosus as integrated predators of mosquitoes in tire habitats in Queensland	Journal of the American Mosquito Control Association	Oceania	Naturalistic Observation	Naturalistic	Mosquito, Copepods	Larvae	Aedes, Culex	N/A
(Calliari, et al., 2003)	Comparison of the predation rate of freshwater cyclopoid copepod species on larvae of the mosquito Culex pipiens	Medical and Veterinary Entomology	South America	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Copepods	Larvae	Aedes	N/A
(Canyon & Hii, 1997)	The gecko: an environmentally friendly biological	Medical and Veterinary Entomology	Oceania	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Geckoes	Adult Mosquitoes	Aedes, Culex, Anopheles	N/A

	agent for mosquito control								
(Cavalcanti, et al., 2007)	Efficacy of fish as predators of <i>Aedes aegypti</i> larvae, under laboratory conditions	Revista de Saude Publica	South America	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Fish	Larvae	<i>Aedes</i>	N/A
(Chae, et al., 2014)	Predation and control efficacies of <i>Misgurnus mizolepis</i> (Cypriniformes: Cobitidae) toward <i>Culex pipiens molestus</i> (Diptera: Culicidae) and fish toxicity of temephos in laboratory and septic tank conditions	Journal of Medical Entomology	Asia	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Fish	Larvae	<i>Culex</i>	N/A
(Banerjee, et al., 2008)	Biocontrol of larval mosquitoes by <i>Acilius sulcatus</i> (Coleoptera: Dytiscidae)	BMC Infectious Diseases	Asia	Controlled Trial	Both	Beetles	Larvae	<i>Culex</i>	N/A
(Chatterjee, Ghosh, & Chandra, 2007)	Eco-friendly control of mosquito larvae by <i>Brachytron pratense</i> nymph	Journal of Environmental Health	Asia	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Dragonfly	Larvae	<i>Anopheles</i>	Malaria
(Cuthbert, Callaghan & Dick, 2019)	The Effect of the Alternative Prey, <i>Paramecium caudatum</i> (Peniculida: Parameciidae), on the Predation of <i>Culex pipiens</i> (Diptera: Culicidae) by the Copepods <i>Macrocyclus albidus</i>	Journal of Medical Entomology	Europe	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Copepods	Larvae	<i>Culex</i>	N/A

	and Megacyclops viridis (Cyclopoida: Cyclopidae)								
(Cuthbert, 2018)	Calanoid Copepods: An Overlooked Tool in the Control of Disease Vector Mosquitoes	Journal of Medical Entomology	Africa	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Copepods	Larvae	Culex	MBDs
(Dieng, et al., 2003)	Life history effects of prey choice by copepods: implications for biocontrol of vector mosquitoes	Journal of the American Mosquito Control Association	Asia	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Copepods	Larvae	Anopheles, Aedes, Culex	N/A
(Dieng, et al., 2017)	Presence of a predator image in potential breeding sites and oviposition responses of a dengue vector	Acta Tropica	Asia	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Fish	Multiple Stages	Aedes	Dengue
(Dieng, et al., 2002)	A laboratory and field evaluation of Macrocyclus distinctus, Megacyclops viridis and Mesocyclops pehpeiensis as control agents of the dengue vector Aedes albopictus in a peridomestic area in Nagasaki, Japan	Medical and Veterinary Entomology	Asia	Controlled Trial	Both	Copepods	Larvae	Aedes	Dengue
(Santos, & Andrade, 1997)	Survey of cyclopids (Crustacea, Copepoda) in Brazil and preliminary screening of their potential as	Revista de Saude Publica	South America	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Copepods	Larvae	Aedes	Dengue

	dengue vector predators								
(Duque, Muñoz & Navarro-Silva, 2004)	A simulation model for the control of the <i>Aedes aegypti</i> , the mosquito vector of dengue and yellow fever, by the crustacean <i>Mesocyclops</i> spp	Rev Salud Publica (Bogota)	South America	Controlled Trial	Simulation	Copepods	Larvae	<i>Aedes</i>	Yellow Fever, Dengue
(Eba, et al., 2021)	Bio-Control of Anopheles Mosquito Larvae Using Invertebrate Predators to Support Human Health Programs in Ethiopia	International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	Africa	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Backswimmers, Dragonfly	Larvae	Anopheles	N/A
(Eitam & Blaustein, 2004)	Oviposition habitat selection by mosquitoes in response to predator (<i>Notonecta maculata</i>) density	Journal of Vector Ecology	Asia	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Backswimmers	Eggs	<i>Culex</i>	N/A
(Focks, 2007)	Toxorhynchites as biocontrol agents	Journal of the American Mosquito Control Association	North America	Review	N/A	Mosquitoes	Multiple Stages	N/A	MBDs
(Griffin, 2014)	Laboratory evaluation of predation on mosquito larvae by Australian mangrove fish	Journal of Vector Ecology	Oceania	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Fish	Larvae	<i>Aedes</i>	N/A
(Howard, Zhou &	Malaria mosquito control using edible fish in western Kenya:	BMC public health	Africa	Controlled Trial	Naturalistic	Fish	Larvae	Anopheles	Malaria

Omlin, 2007)	preliminary findings of a controlled study								
(Imbahale , et al., 2011)	Development of environmental tools for anopheline larval control	Parasites & Vectors	Africa	Naturalistic Observation	Naturalistic	Fish	Larvae	Anopheles	Malaria
(Irwin, & Paskewitz , 2009)	Investigation of fathead minnows (Pimephales promelas) as a biological control agent of Culex mosquitoes under laboratory and field conditions	Journal of the American Mosquito Control Association	North America	Controlled Trial	Both	Fish	Larvae	Culex	N/A
(Kesavara ju & Juliano, 2004)	Differential Behavioral Responses to Water-Borne Cues to Predation in Two Container-Dwelling Mosquitoes	Annals of the Entomologic al Society of America	North America	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Mosquito	Larvae	Aedes	N/A
(Khan, et al., 2022)	The role of selected odonate nymphs in biological control of Culex quinquefasciatus larvae, and effect of glyphosate herbicide on their predatory performance	International Journal of Tropical Insect Science	Asia	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Dragonfly	Larvae	Aedes	MBDs
(Kroeger, Liess, & Duquesne , 2014)	Temporal and spatial habitat preferences and biotic interactions between mosquito larvae and antagonistic crustaceans in the field	Journal of Vector Ecology	Europe	Naturalistic Observation	Naturalistic	Copepods	Larvae	Culex	N/A

(Kumar, et al., 2014)	Predatory potential of <i>Platynectes</i> sp. (Coleoptera: Dytiscidae) on <i>Aedes albopictus</i> , the vector of dengue/chikungunya in Kerala, India	Tropical Biomedicine	Asia	Naturalistic Observation	Naturalistic	Beetles	Larvae	<i>Aedes</i>	N/A
(Kumar & Hwang, 2006)	Larvicidal efficiency of aquatic predators: A perspective for mosquito biocontrol	Journal of Vector Ecology	Oceania	Review	N/A	N/A	Multiple Stages	N/A	MBDs
(Kumar & Ramakrishna, 2003)	Predation on Mosquito Larvae by <i>Mesocyclops thermocycloides</i> (Copepoda: Cyclopoida) in the Presence of Alternate Prey	Physiological Entomology	Asia	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Copepods	Larvae	<i>Anopheles</i>	N/A
(Kusumawathie, et al., 2008)	Larvivorous potential of the guppy, <i>Poecilia reticulata</i> , in anopheline mosquito control in riverbed pools below the Kotmale dam, Sri Lanka	Asia Pacific Journal of Public Health	Asia	Controlled Trial	Naturalistic	Fish	Larvae	<i>Anopheles</i>	MBDs
(Alison & Cech, 1990)	Prey selection by mosquitofish (<i>Gambusia affinis</i>) in California rice fields: effect of vegetation and prey species	Journal of the American Mosquito Control Association	North America	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Fish	Larvae	<i>Culex</i>	N/A

(Louca, et al., 2014)	Role of fish as predators of mosquito larvae on the floodplain of the Gambia River	Journal of Medical Entomology	Africa	Naturalistic Observation	Naturalistic	Fish	Larvae	Anopheles	MBDs
(Lundkvist, et al., 2003)	Diving beetles (Dytiscidae) as predators of mosquito larvae (Culicidae) in field experiments and in laboratory tests of prey preference	Bulletin Entomological Research	Europe	Controlled Trial	Both	Beetles	Larvae	Culex	N/A
(Malla et al., 2023)	Numerical analysis of predatory potentiality of <i>Toxorhynchites splendens</i> against larval <i>Aedes albopictus</i> in laboratory and semi-field conditions	Scientific Reports	Asia	Controlled Trial	Both	Mosquito	Larvae	Aedes	N/A
(Mandal, et al., 2008)	Biocontrol efficiency of odonate nymphs against larvae of the mosquito, <i>Culex quinquefasciatus</i> Say, 1823	Acta Tropica	Asia	Controlled Trial	Both	Dragonfly	Adult Mosquitoes	Culex	N/A
(Manna, Aditya & Banerjee, 2008)	Vulnerability of the mosquito larvae to the guppies (<i>Poecilia reticulata</i>) in the presence of alternative preys	Journal of Vector Borne Diseases	Asia	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Fish	Larvae	Culex	N/A
(Marten, 2007)	Turtles	Journal of the American Mosquito	South America	Controlled Trial	Both	Turtles	Larvae	N/A	N/A

		Control Association							
(Marti, et al., 2004)	Evaluation of <i>Mesocyclops annulatus</i> (Copepoda: Cyclopoidea) as a control agent of <i>Aedes aegypti</i> (Diptera: Culicidae) in Argentina	Memórias do Instituto Oswaldo Cruz	South America	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Copepods	Larvae	<i>Aedes</i>	N/A
(Matias & Adrias, 2010)	The use of annual killifish in the biocontrol of the aquatic stages of mosquitoes in temporary bodies of fresh water; a potential new tool in vector control	Parasites & Vectors	Africa	Controlled Trial	Naturalistic	Fish	Multiple Stages	<i>Culex</i>	N/A
(Murugan , et al., 2015)	<i>Datura metel</i> -synthesized silver nanoparticles magnify predation of dragonfly nymphs against the malaria vector <i>Anopheles stephensi</i>	Parasitology Research	Africa	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Dragonfly	Larvae	<i>Anopheles</i>	Malaria
(Nam, et al., 2000)	National progress in dengue vector control in Vietnam: Survey for <i>Mesocyclops</i> (Copepoda), <i>Micronecta</i> (Corixidae), and fish as biological control agents	Medical and Veterinary Entomology	Asia	Naturalistic Observation	Both	Copepods, Fish	Multiple Stages	<i>Aedes</i>	Dengue

(Nelson, & Jackson, 2006)	A predator from East Africa that chooses malaria vectors as preferred prey	PLoS One	Africa	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Spider	Adult Mosquitoes	Anopheles	Malaria
(Nyamah, Sulaiman, & Omar, 2011)	Field observation on the efficacy of <i>Toxorhynchites splendens</i> (Wiedemann) as a biocontrol agent against <i>Aedes albopictus</i> (Skuse) larvae in a cemetery	Tropical Biomedicine	Asia	Naturalistic Observation	Naturalistic	Mosquito	Larvae	Aedes	Dengue
(Ohba, et al., 2011)	Heteropteran insects as mosquito predators in water jars in southern Vietnam	Journal of Vector Ecology	Asia	Naturalistic Observation	Naturalistic	Heteropteran Insects	Larvae	Aedes	MBDs
(Okorie & Abiodun, 2010)	Laboratory evaluation of the biocontrol potential of <i>Aphyosemion gularis</i> against <i>Anopheles</i> larvae	Journal of Vector Borne Diseases	Africa	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Fish	Larvae	Anopheles	Malaria
(Ong'wen , Onyango & Bukhari, 2020)	Direct and indirect effects of predation and parasitism on the <i>Anopheles gambiae</i> mosquito	Parasites & Vectors	Africa	Review, Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Dragonfly, Parasites	Pupae	Anopheles	Malaria
(Panogadi a-Reyes, Cruz & Bautista, 2004)	Philippine species of <i>Mesocyclops</i> (crustacea: Copepoda) as a biological control agent of <i>Aedes aegypti</i> (Linnaeus)	Dengue Bulletin	Asia	Controlled Trial	Both	Copepods	Larvae	Aedes	Dengue

(Pernia, De Roa & Palacios-Cáceres, 2007)	Prey-predator relationship between the cyclopoids Mesocyclops longisetus and Mesocyclops meridianus with Anopheles aquasalis larvae	Journal of the American Mosquito Control Association	South America	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Copepods	Larvae	Anopheles	N/A
(Quiroz Martínez & Rodríguez Castro, 2007)	Aquatic insects as predators of mosquito larvae	Journal of the American Mosquito Control Association	North America	Review	N/A	N/A	Multiple Stages	N/A	MBDs
(Ramanibai & Kan niga, 2008)	Laboratory evaluation of Mesocyclops aspericornis as a biocontrol agent of Aedes aegypti	Dengue Bulletin	Asia	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Copepods	Larvae	Aedes	N/A
(Ranathunge, et al., 2019)	Use of cyclopoid copepods for control of Anopheles (Diptera: Culicidae) mosquito larvae to prevent re-emergence of malaria in Sri Lanka	Journal of Vector Borne Diseases	Asia	Controlled Trial	Both	Copepods	Larvae	Anopheles	Malaria
(Rawlins, et al., 1997)	Evaluation of Caribbean strains of Macrocyclus and Mesocyclops (Cyclopoida:Cyclopida e) as biological control tools for the dengue vector Aedes aegypti	Journal of the American Mosquito Control Association	South America	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Copepods	Larvae	Aedes	Dengue

(Rey, et al., 2004)	Laboratory and field studies of <i>Macrocyclus albidus</i> (Crustacea: Copepoda) for biological control of mosquitoes in artificial containers in a subtropical environment	Journal of Vector Ecology	North America	Controlled Trial	Both	Copepods	Larvae	Aedes	N/A
(Roberts, 1995)	Salt-marsh Crustaceans, <i>Gammarus duebeni</i> and <i>Palaemonetes varians</i> as Predators of Mosquito Larvae and Their Reaction to <i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i> subsp. <i>israelensis</i>	Biocontrol Science and Technology	Europe	Naturalistic Observation	Naturalistic	Copepods	Larvae	Aedes	N/A
(Rojas-Sahagún, et al., 2012)	Predatory capacity of <i>Macrobrachium tenellum</i> on <i>Aedes aegypti</i> larvae in lab conditions	Revista Cubana Medicina Tropical	North America	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Prawns	Larvae	Aedes	N/A
(Russell, et al., 2001)	Laboratory evaluation of two native fishes from tropical North Queensland as biological control agents of subterranean <i>Aedes aegypti</i>	Journal of the American Mosquito Control Association	Oceania	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Fish	Larvae	Aedes	N/A
(Russel, Muir, Weinstein, & Kay, 1996)	Surveillance of the mosquito <i>Aedes aegypti</i> and its biocontrol with the copepod <i>Mesocyclops aspericornis</i> in	Medical and Veterinary Entomology	Oceania	Naturalistic Observation	Naturalistic	Copepods	Larvae	Aedes	N/A

	Australian wells and gold mines								
Russell, et al., 2021)	Size, not temperature, drives cyclopoid copepod predation of invasive mosquito larvae	PLoS One	Europe	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Copepods	Larvae	Aedes	N/A
(Saleeza, Norma-Rashid, & Sofian-Azirun, 2014)	Guppies as predators of common mosquito larvae in Malaysia	Southeast Asian Journal of Tropical Medicine and Public Health	Asia	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Fish	Larvae	Culex, Aedes	N/A
(Samannali, et al., 2018)	Larvicidal Potential of Five Selected Dragonfly Nymphs in Sri Lanka over Aedes aegypti (Linnaeus) Larvae under Laboratory Settings	BioMed Research International	Asia	Controlled Trial	Naturalistic	Dragonfly	Larvae	Aedes	N/A
(Schaper, 1999)	Evaluation of costarican copepods (crustacea: EUDECAPODA) for larval Aedes Aegypti control with special reference to MESOCYCLOPS THERMOCYCLOPOIDES	Journal of the American Mosquito Control Association	North America	Controlled Trial	Both	Copepods	Larvae	Aedes	N/A
(Schreiber, 2007)	Toxorhynchites	Journal of the American Mosquito	North America	Review	N/A	Mosquitoes	Larvae	N/A	MBDs

		Control Association								
(Shaalán, et al., 2007)	A mosquito predator survey in Townsville, Australia, and an assessment of <i>Diplonychus</i> sp. and <i>Anisops</i> sp. predatorial capacity against <i>Culex annulirostris</i> mosquito immatures	Journal of Vector Ecology	Oceania	Naturalistic Observation	Naturalistic	Backswimmers, Water bugs	Larvae	N/A	N/A	
(Shaalán & Canyon, 2009)	Aquatic insect predators and mosquito control	Tropical Biomedicine	Oceania	Review	N/A	N/A	Multiple Stages	N/A	MBDs	
(Shafique, et al., 2019)	Implementation of guppy fish (<i>Poecilia reticulata</i>), and a novel larvicide (Pyriproxyfen) product (Sumilarv 2MR) for dengue control in Cambodia: a qualitative study of acceptability, sustainability and community engagement	PLoS neglected tropical diseases	Asia	Controlled Trial, Naturalistic Observation	Both	Fish	Larvae	Aedes	Dengue	
(Silberbusch, Abramsky & Tsurim, 2015)	Effects of fish cues on mosquito larvae development	Acta Tropica	Asia	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Fish	Eggs	Aedes, Culex	N/A	

(Soltani, Chouahda & Smagghe, 2008)	Evaluation of halofenozide against prey mosquito larvae Culex pipiens and the predator fish Gambusia affinis: impact on growth and enzymatic activities	Communications in agricultural and applied biological sciences	Africa	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Fish	Larvae	Culex	N/A
(Stav, Blaustein, & Margalit, 2000)	Influence of nymphal Anax imperator (Odonata: Aeshnidae) on oviposition by the mosquito Culiseta longiareolata (Diptera: Culicidae) and community structure in temporary pools	Journal of Vector Ecology	Asia	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Dragonfly	Adult Mosquitoes	Other	N/A
(Tikasingh, 1992)	Effects of Toxorhynchites moctezuma larval predation on Aedes aegypti populations: experimental evaluation	Medical and Veterinary Entomology	Europe	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Mosquito	Larvae	Aedes	N/A
(Tran, et al., 2016)	Evolution determines how global warming and pesticide exposure will shape predator-prey interactions with vector mosquitoes	Marine and Freshwater Research	Europe	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Flies	Larvae	Culex	Dengue
(Tranchida, et al., 2009)	Predation potential of three flatworm species (Platyhelminthes: Turbellaria) on mosquitoes (Diptera: Culicidae)	Biological Control	South America	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Flatworms	Larvae	Aedes	N/A

(Trpis & Gerberg, 1993)	Laboratory colonization of <i>Toxorhynchites brevipalpis</i>	Bulletin World Health Organ	Africa	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Mosquito	Larvae	Aedes	Dengue
(Tuno, Phong & Takagi, 2020)	Climate Change May Restrict the Predation Efficiency of <i>Mesocyclops aspericornis</i> (Copepoda: Cyclopidae) on <i>Aedes aegypti</i> (Diptera: Culicidae) Larvae	Insects	Asia	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Copepods	Larvae	Aedes	MBDs
(Udayanga, et al., 2019)	Predatory efficacy of five locally available copepods on <i>Aedes</i> larvae under laboratory settings: An approach towards bio-control of dengue in Sri Lanka	PLoS One	Asia	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Copepods	Larvae	Aedes	MBDs
(Van Dam & Walton, 2007)	Comparison of mosquito control provided by the arroyo chub (<i>Gila orcutti</i>) and the mosquitofish (<i>Gambusia affinis</i>)	Journal of the American Mosquito Control Association	North America	Controlled Trial	Naturalistic	Fish	Larvae	N/A	N/A
(Van Dam & Walton, 2008)	The effect of predatory fish exudates on the ovipositional behaviour of three mosquito species: <i>Culex quinquefasciatus</i> , <i>Aedes aegypti</i> and <i>Culex tarsalis</i>	Medical and Veterinary Entomology	North America	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Fish	Eggs	<i>Culex</i>	N/A

(Van Uiregt, Hurst & Wilson, 2012)	Reduced size and starvation resistance in adult mosquitoes, <i>Aedes notoscriptus</i> , exposed to predation cues as larvae	Journal of Animal Ecology	Oceania	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Fish	Multiple Stages	<i>Aedes</i>	N/A
(Walshe, et al., 2017)	Larvivorous fish for preventing malaria transmission	Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews	North America	Review	N/A	Fish	Larvae	<i>Anopheles</i>	Malaria
(Washburn, 1995)	Regulatory factors affecting larval mosquito populations in container and pool habitats: implications for biological control.	Journal of the American Mosquito Control Association	North America	Review	N/A	N/A	Larvae	N/A	N/A
(Wattal, Adak, Dhiman, & Sharma, 1996)	The biology and predatory potential of notonectid bug, <i>Enithares indica</i> (Fabr) against mosquito larvae	Southeast Asian Journal of Tropical Medicine and Public Health	Asia	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Backswimmers	Larvae	<i>Aedes</i> , <i>Culicinae</i> , Other	N/A
(Weiser, 1963)	Advances in biological control in relation to vectors of human diseases	Bulletin World Health Organ	Global	Review	N/A	N/A	Multiple Stages	N/A	MBDs
(Why, Lara & Walton, 2016)	Oviposition of <i>Culex tarsalis</i> (Diptera: Culicidae) Differs on Water Conditioned by Potential Fish and Insect Predators	Journal of Medical Entomology	North America	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Fish	Eggs	<i>Culex</i>	N/A

(Willems, Webb & Russell, 2005)	Tadpoles of four common Australian frogs are not effective predators of the common pest and vector mosquito <i>Culex annulirostris</i>	Journal of the American Mosquito Control Association	Oceania	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Tadpoles	Larvae	<i>Culex</i>	N/A
(Zuharah, Fadzly & Lester, 2013)	Lethal and sublethal impacts of predaceous backswimmer <i>Anisops wakefieldi</i> (Hemiptera: Notonectidae) on the life-history traits of the New Zealand mosquito <i>Culex pervigilans</i> (Diptera: Culicidae)	Journal of Medical Entomology	Oceania	Controlled Trial	Naturalistic	Backswimmers	Larvae	<i>Culex</i>	N/A
(Zuharah, et al., 2017)	Oviposition Habitat Selection of Dengue Vectors, <i>Aedes aegypti</i> and <i>Aedes albopictus</i> in Response to Fish Predator	Tropical Life Science Research	Asia	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Fish	Larvae	<i>Aedes</i>	N/A
(Zuharah et al., 2015)	Risky behaviors: effects of <i>Toxorhynchites splendens</i> (Diptera: Culicidae) predator on the behavior of three mosquito species	Journal of Insect Science	Asia	Controlled Trial	Laboratory	Mosquito	Larvae	<i>Aedes</i> , <i>Anopheles</i>	N/A